

Vedlegg til rapporten "Tilgang, grensesnitt, data og metadata: Rapport om forskernes behov for dataplattform"

Disse vedleggene dokumenterer metode og grunnlag for datainnsamling og analyse til rapporten «Tilgang, grensesnitt, data og metadata: Rapport om forskernes behov for dataplattform».¹

Vedlegg A: Metode for utforming av spørreundersøkelse

Vedlegg B: Samtaleguide for semi-strukturerte intervjuer

Vedlegg C: Skjema for spørreundersøkelse

Vedlegg D: Survey results

¹ Tønnessen, Jon (2026): *Tilgang, grensesnitt, data og metadata: Rapport om forskernes behov for dataplattform*. DOI:[10.5281/zenodo.20749205](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20749205).

Vedlegg A: Metode for utforming av spørreundersøkelse

Skjemaet for undersøkelsen ble utformet i tråd med Bethlehem & Biffignandis (2021, 237-289) veikart for nettbaserte spørreskjema. Dette innebærer forhåndstesting, vurdering av hvordan prosjektet presenteres og utforming av nødvendige instruksjoner. Skjemaet ble utformet med logisk forgreining, slik at respondentene i størst mulig grad bare har besvart spørsmål med relevans for dem selv. Formålet har både vært å øke gjennomføringsgraden, og sikre svarenes relevans og dermed resultatenes kvalitet.

Det ble samlet inn grunnleggende informasjon om respondentenes stillingstittel, arbeidssted og undervisning for å gi mulighet til å analysere og anslå betydningen av ulike bakgrunnsvariabler. Resten av undersøkelsen besto av spørsmål med en psykometrisk Likert-skala, samt frie tekstsvar for hver seksjon, slik at respondentene kunne utdype eller legge til viktige aspekter det ikke ble spurt om.

For Likert-skalerte spørsmål ble respondentene bedt om å rangere viktigheten av ulike variabler etter følgende ordinale skala:

Svært viktig – Ganske viktig – Ingen mening – Mindre viktig – Ikke viktig.

Respondentene ble også gitt en forklaring på hva disse ulike kategoriene betød i undersøkelsens kontekst:

Du vil nå bli spurt om dine behov for tilgang. Du svarer ved å angi hvor viktig eller uviktig noe er for din forskning.

SVÆRT VIKTIG betyr at du er helt avhengig av dette. Infrastrukturen vil være verdiløs for deg uten dette.

GANSKE VIKTIG er et behov som bør dekkes, men det kan komme etter en stund.

MINDRE VIKTIG innebærer at det vil ha verdi, men ikke er avgjørende for om du kan bruke infrastrukturen.

IKKE VIKTIG betyr at alternativet ikke vil ha noen verdi for deg i dag eller i nær framtid.

*Dersom du ikke vet eller ikke har noen mening kan du velge **Ingen mening**.*

Vedlegg B: Samtaleguide for semi-strukturerte intervjuer

Dette er en samtaleguide for intervju av informanter til WebDatas behovsstudie, del 1.

Intervjuene gjennomføres som semi-strukturerte samtaler der det legges opp til at informanten får snakke så fritt og selvstendig som mulig, og dermed tar opp det informanten selv mener er vesentlig. Informanten bes sette av inntil 60 minutter til intervjuet, men varigheten søkes å begrenset til 45 minutter.

For hver fase oppsummerer intervjueren sin forståelse gjennom å spørre om om hen har forstått informanten riktig, samt om det er noe informanten vil legge til.

Fase 1: Rammesetting

(5-7 min)

Etablere kontakt

- Uformell prat om prosjektet og etablere kontakt.

Informasjon

- Forklarer samtalens formål
- Forklarer hva innsamlet data brukes til, og at informasjon kan sammenstilles og gjengis pseudonymisert i en åpen rapport
- Spør om noe er uklart og om respondenten har noen spørsmål
- Kontrollere at informanten samtykker til opptak for transkripsjonsformål

Fase 2: Bakgrunn

(5-8 min)

1. *Kan du kort beskrive din stilling og hva du gjør i ditt arbeid?*
2. *Hva er din primære fagbakgrunn?*
3. *Har du tidligere erfaring med forskning på innhold eller data fra web? Hvis ja, hvordan og på hvilke medietyper eller format?*

Fase 3: Fokusering mot forskningsbehov

(30-35 min)

4. *Hva er typiske problemer eller forskningsspørsmål du vil forsøke å besvare ved bruk av data fra nett?*
5. *Beskriv hvordan prosessen med å utforske og analysere data ser ut for deg. Hvilke metoder, teknikker og verktøy kan du finne på å benytte?*
6. *Hvilken del av vasking og rensing vil du gjøre selv, og hva vil du at en infrastruktur tar hånd om?*
7. *Hvilke metadata er viktige for deg når du skal identifisere eller skjære til et sett med relevante data for forskning?*
8. *Kan du beskrive din metodiske verktøykasse?*
9. *Hvor viktig er informasjon om opphavsrett og lisens for videre bruk?*

Fase 4: Avslutning og krystallisering av nøkkelbehov

(5-10 min)

10. *Har du spesifikke behov eller ønsker som vi ikke har snakket om?*
11. *Beskriv drømmescenariot når du skal arbeide med NBs samling av arkiverte nettdata.*

Vedlegg C: Skjema for spørreundersøkelse

Spørreskjemaet eksisterte både på norsk og engelsk. Den engelske versjonen er tatt vare på siden den har blitt etterspurt av andre institusjoner som ønsker å replikere arbeidet vi har gjort med sine egne brukere. Derfor deles den engelske versjonen også i denne rapporten.

I have read and accept that my answers are processed as described in the declaration of consent.
(input:checkbox)

--- YOUR ROLE ---

Which type of institution are you affiliated with? (input:radio)

- University / University College
- Research organisation
- Government authority or administration

Which university or university college? (input:radio)

- List of most common universities
- Other -> (input:text)

Which research organisation? (input:radio)

- List of most common research org.
- Other -> (input:text)

Which term best describes your field of research? (input:checkbox; max. 2 choices)

- Humanities
- Social Sciences
- Economics
- Natural Sciences & Mathematics
- Pedagogics
- Law
- Medicine

What is your primary academic discipline?

(input:text)

What is your job title? (input:radio)

- Archivist
- Librarian
- Researcher
- Research Assistant
- Associate Professor
- Senior Lecturer
- Engineer
- Postdoctoral Researcher
- Professor / Docent
- Adviser / Consultant
- Doctoral Candidate (or PhD Student)
- Lecturer
- Other -> (input:text)

Is teaching or supervision of students part of your work? (input:radio)

- Yes
- No

You have stated that you teach or supervise students. At which level? (input:checkbox; max. 3 choices)

- Bachelor
- Master
- Phd
- Other -> (input:text)

--- ACCESS ---

When searching, exploring and analysing data, how important is it for you to have access to:
(input:likert scale)

- Metadata (e.g. language, identifiers, media type)
- Aggregated data (e.g. statistics, charts)
- Short derivatives (e.g. keywords in context, thumbnails)
- The entire document (e.g. via a viewing service)

When searching, exploring and analysing data, how important is it for you to have access from:
(input:likert scale)

- The National Library's premises
- University campus
- Research organisation
- Home office

Do you have other access-related needs? Please describe them in the text field below.
(input:text)

--- INTERFACES ---

When searching, exploring and analysing data, how important is it for you to do it from the following type of unit: (input:likert scale)

- Desktop or laptop computer
- Tablet
- Mobile phone

When searching, exploring and analysing data, how important are the following interfaces to you:
(input:likert scale)

- Web browser
- API or notebooks
- Software installed on your own computer

For search and exploration, how important are the following functionalities? (input:likert scale)

- Full-text search
- Advanced search (Boolean operators, proximity search, filtering, etc.)
- Search using an uploaded image
- Visualisation of search results
- Playback/viewing of individual pages
- Curated collections
- Define datasets based on searches (e.g. building a corpus)
- Export files for reference management (Zotero, EndNote)
- Citation suggestions (APA, Chicago)
- Links to other archives (e.g. Internet Archive)

If you use software for analysis, how important are the following: (input:likert scale)

- Jupyter Notebook or similar
- Gephi
- Orange
- Voyant
- NVivo
- Other software -> (input:text)

Are there other software tools that are important when you analyse data? Please list the names of the programs, separated by commas:
(input:text)

--- DATA ---

How important are the following media types for your research? (input:likert scale)

- Text
- Images
- Audio
- Video
- Web pages as objects (holistic representation)
- Source code

How important are the following types of content to your research? (input:likert scale)

- Content from public authorities
- News with a responsible editor
- Magazines and non-academic journals
- Academic journals
- Content from organisations and associations
- Content from companies and other legal entities
- Blogs and personal websites
- Podcasts
- Social media
- Streaming video (YouTube, etc.)

Are there other categories of web material that are important for your research? Please list them, separated by commas:

(input:text)

--- METADATA ---

How important are the following administrative and bibliographical metadata for your research? (input:likert scale)

- Persistent identifier for the object (DOI, handle, URN, etc.)
- Name of creator (photographer, author, etc.)
- Title of publication
- Title of document
- Place of editorial responsibility
- Date/time of harvesting
- Estimated date of publication
- Other resources with identical content
- Other resources with approximately similar content
- Access conditions
- Licence for further use

--- METADATA: Text ---

How important are the following metadata about text for your research? (input:likert scale)

- Language (Norwegian, Sámi, English, etc.)
- Text length (number of words)
- Format (HTML, DOCX, PDF, etc.)
- Links to other documents
- Other documents that link to this document
- Enriched metadata (e.g. sentiment, topics, events)
- Linguistic annotation (parts of speech, sentence structure)

Are there other types of metadata about text that are important for your research? Please specify: (input:text)

Would you like to rank the importance of different types of metadata for images? (input:radio)

- Yes
- No

--- METADATA: Images ---

How important are the following metadata about images for your research? (input:likert scale)

- Image type (photograph, illustration, chart, icon)
- Image title
- Size (measured in pixels)
- File format (PNG, JPG, GIF, etc.)
- Geographical location (where the image was taken)
- Links to pages where the image has been used
- Text surrounding the image
- Objects in the image (e.g. people, nature, faces)
- Visually similar motifs
- Semantically similar motifs
- Colours
- Image framing (close-up, wide shot, etc.)
- Image description from HTML

Are there other types of metadata about images that are important for your research? Please specify:
(input:text)

Would you like to rank the importance of different types of metadata for audio? (input:radio)
Yes
No

--- METADATA: Audio ---

How important are the following metadata about audio for your research? (input:likert scale)
Audio type (speech, music, ambient sound, sound effect, etc.)
Title of the audio resource
Duration
Technical attributes (file format, codec, bitrate)
Enriched metadata (e.g. transcription, genre, etc.)
Links to pages where the audio has been used
Language (for speech/vocals)

Are there other types of metadata about audio that are important for your research? Please specify:
(input:text)

Would you like to rank the importance of different types of metadata for video? (input:radio)
Yes
No

--- METADATA: Video ---

How important are the following metadata about video for your research? (input:likert scale)
Title
Duration
Technical attributes (file format, codec, bitrate)
Enriched metadata (e.g. audio transcription, objects in the image, genre classification, etc.)
Links to pages where the video has been used
Language (for speech/vocals)

Are there other types of metadata about video that are important for your research? Please specify:
(input:text)

Would you like to rank the importance of different types of metadata for source code? (input:radio)
Yes
No

--- METADATA: Source Code ---

How important are the following metadata about source code for your research? (input:likert scale)
Programming language
Technical attributes (format, dependencies, version information)
Links to content where the code has been used
Size (e.g. data volume, number of lines of code)

Are there other types of metadata about source code that are important for your research? Please specify:
(input:text)

--- ADDITIONAL COMMENTS ---

Do you have any other needs or comments that we have not asked about? Please describe them here:
(input:text)

Would you like to receive news from WebData, including information about workshops or service launches?
(input:radio)
Yes -> (input:valid_email)
No

Background

The results presented here are part of a WebData's needs assessment. By identifying and prioritising researchers' needs, we aim to inform the development of the research infrastructure's data platform.

In addition to a survey, we've interviewed 12 key stakeholders and held two workshops where respondents participated in discussing the results.

The survey was developed according to Biffignandi & Bethlehem's (2021) road map for web surveys. The questionnaire was distributed in selected communities, primarily targeting researchers in the digital humanities and computational social sciences. A main motivation for this was ensure relevant responses from a group of respondents that with a high probability are interested in using the research infrastructure.

Questions focused on four main themes:

- Access
- Interface
- Data
- Metadata

Responses were collected through an online questionnaire between 14 Oct 2025 and 6 Feb 2026. Some profile data and free text responses have been omitted from the publicly shared dataset to protect respondent anonymity.

Respondents

87

Completion time

Average

11:44

Median

09:50

Which term best describes your research area? (Up to two answers possible)

Do you have teaching or supervision of students as part of your work tasks?

- Yes
- No

You have indicated that you teach or supervise students. At what level? (Multiple answers possible)

When you search, explore, or analyse data, how important is it that the infrastructure provides you access to

Very important Quite important No opinion Less important Not important

When you search, explore, and analyse data, how important is it for you to have access from the following locations?

Very important Quite important No opinion Less important Not important

When you search, explore, and analyse data, how important is the following device?

■ Very important
 ■ Quite important
 ■ No opinion
 ■ Less important
 ■ Not important

When you search, explore, and analyse data, how important is the following interface for you?

Very important Quite important No opinion Less important Not important

For search and exploration, how important is the following functionality to you?

Very important Quite important No opinion Less important Not important

If you use software for analysis, how important is the following?

How important are these media types to your research?

How important are these categories of web content for your research?

How important are the following administrative and bibliographic metadata to you?

Very important Quite important No opinion Less important Not important

How important is the following rights information to you?

■ Very important
 ■ Quite important
 ■ No opinion
 ■ Less important
 ■ Not important

How important is this metadata about text content to you?

■ Very important
 ■ Quite important
 ■ No opinion
 ■ Less important
 ■ Not important

Do you want to prioritise the importance of metadata for images?

■ No
■ Yes

How important is this metadata about images to you?

Do you want to prioritise the importance of metadata for audio?

How important is this metadata about audio to you?

Do you want to prioritise the importance of metadata for video?

How important is this metadata about video to you?

Very important Quite important No opinion Less important Not important

Do you want to prioritise the importance of metadata for source code?

How important is this metadata about source code to you?

